

ON THE POLITICS OF HYDROGEN ECONOMY, POWER-TO-X, AND DECARBONIZATION

George Tsatsaronis

Centre for Sustainable Energy, National Centre for Scientific Research “Demokritos”,
email: g.tsatsaronis@ipta.demokritos.gr

ABSTRACT

Since the 1970s, hydrogen has been considered an essential element of a future energy economy. Recently, within the framework of decarbonization in the energy sector, many countries have developed national plans to address the establishment of a hydrogen-based economy in the *near* future. To achieve complete decarbonization, electric power must be generated exclusively from renewable sources. Power-to-X (PtX) technologies refer to hydrogen generation from electricity and its subsequent conversion to another energy carrier for storage or transportation. Thus, the challenges associated with establishing a green hydrogen-based economy include those associated with expanding renewable energies and the production, transportation, and storage of the energy carriers denoted by X in the PtX.

A prerequisite for decarbonization enabled by the hydrogen economy is the availability of large quantities of excess “green” electricity. In the coming decades, we will be far from reaching this goal. Thus, almost all current efforts toward establishing a hydrogen economy tend to increase CO₂ emissions globally instead of decreasing them because the incremental electricity generation required for hydrogen production is accomplished using fossil fuels.

As long as fossil fuels are used on a large scale to cover the demand for electricity in a country, the implementation of a hydrogen economy will lead to a significant increase in the inefficiencies, costs, and CO₂ emissions in the energy sector of the same country compared to other options that either are or could easily become available. As long as the conditions for generating large additional amounts of green electricity are not met, a hydrogen economy is counterproductive to the decarbonization efforts.

Therefore, national energy policies should focus in the coming years on the expansion of the use of renewable energy sources, as well as on the expansion of the electric grids and of the interconnections among countries, which are very important for achieving the decarbonization goals faster and in a sustainable way. The use of hydrogen and PtX technologies should not be promoted now with taxpayers money (to maximize decarbonization per unit of invested capital), but in later years, when the share of green electricity in a country reaches very high levels. Finally policymakers, scientists and engineers should (a) expand and reconsider the existing measures for reducing CO₂ emissions in the energy sector, (b) objectively inform the public about the available options, and (c) stop misleading the public about the role of hydrogen in decarbonization in the near future.

Keywords: Energy policy; Decarbonization; Hydrogen economy; Power-to-X (PtX).

1. INTRODUCTION

Despite a series of international meetings since the beginning of the 1990s, international agreements (e.g., in Rio de Janeiro, Kyoto, and Paris), and continuous warnings by experts in climate change, the worldwide CO₂ emissions have been continuously increasing practically every year until today, with the exception of the short-time effects of the financial crises and the COVID pandemic. As a matter of fact, global CO₂ emissions are today almost twice as high compared with those in the beginning of the 1990s. In the time period 2012 - 2021, the CO₂ emissions increased on average by 0.6% per year [1]. This shows that the measures undertaken so far are insufficient for tackling the problem.

To mitigate the CO₂ impact on climate change, mankind is expected to significantly reduce the net CO₂ emissions from the energy sector to the atmosphere within a few decades in the future. Countries have developed a series of measures aiming at this goal. The most important measures focus on the expansion of the use of renewable energy systems, the reduction in the use of fossil fuels, and the establishment of a hydrogen economy, but not directly on the reduction of the per capita energy use or on the reduction in the rate of increase of world population. The reduction of the worldwide energy demand is extremely important for the reduction of the net CO₂ emissions to the atmosphere. As a result of the continuous increase in the global energy demand, the primary energy supplied by fossil fuels more than doubled between 1990 and today. The failure of most of the industrialized countries that use decarbonization mechanisms (e.g., CO₂ certificates) to significantly reduce their overall CO₂ emissions in the last years shows that additional, more effective measures than the already applied mechanisms are required to mitigate the CO₂ impact on climate change.

All energy plans developed after the first energy crisis in 1973 include hydrogen as an important pillar of a future energy economy. Almost every known process of producing hydrogen has therefore been extensively investigated in the last 50 years and continues to be scrutinized today. The results have never been very encouraging, but hydrogen has nonetheless always been regarded as one of the most important future fuels in all these years. Since pure hydrogen is not provided directly by nature, it is important to consider the primary energy form and the process used for its production, because they both affect efficiency, costs and associated CO₂ emissions. The primary energy sources used for hydrogen production include natural gas, coal, oil, biomass, nuclear energy, solar energy, and wind energy. Every energy resource currently available can theoretically be used for hydrogen production. Today a steam reforming process is still one of the most cost-effective processes, responsible for over 70% of the worldwide hydrogen production.

While carbon capture appears to theoretically be a promising and essential technology for reducing greenhouse gas emissions, there are several challenges and obstacles, including high investment and operating costs, high energy requirements, the lack of public acceptance of transportation of large CO₂ amounts, and the need for identifying and using suitable sites for storing the captured CO₂. Therefore, carbon capture could not yet reach the status of wide commercialization, although Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) and Carbon Capture and Use (CCU) are based on conventional technology. Many countries with large resources of fossil fuels emphasize the CCS/CCU solution, as long as they want to continue exploiting fossil fuels. In the author's opinion, however, CCS and CCU will not have a large contribution to decarbonization in the future because very few industrialized countries (e.g., Norway) will finally employ CCS technologies. Therefore, the use of fossil fuels for hydrogen production should be avoided and is not further considered in this paper.

2. PLANS FOR HYDROGEN

Recently many mainly industrialized countries (among them the USA, Norway, Germany and some other countries of the European Union) decided to proceed with a hydrogen-based energy economy, in order to fight climate change. To achieve this, the hydrogen should be produced using renewable energies, mainly electricity generated by renewable sources (the so-called *green electricity* that leads to the production of *green hydrogen*). In many studies (e.g., [2]), hydrogen is presented as the most practical alternative to reach net-zero CO₂ emissions in the coming decades. It is hoped that by creating a high demand for green hydrogen, water-electrolysis technologies will be adopted rapidly by many countries and, thus, the production costs will be reduced. According to these plans (see also [3]), hydrogen will be produced in regions rich in renewable energy and part of the hydrogen will be transported to other regions, which have a high energy demand. The so obtained hydrogen and its derivatives will be initially used in energy sectors that are hard to decarbonize (for example, steel or cement production and aviation). Plans for establishing a hydrogen pipeline network, based on the existing natural gas pipeline network, are currently under discussion in Europe.

It is true that hydrogen is a fuel which theoretically can be produced in almost any country. This “democratization” of the energy sector is appealing, particularly for countries that depend on fossil fuel imports from other countries. If a hydrogen economy is established, this energy dependence could be reduced, but not eliminated for most countries. In Germany, for example, approximately 90% of the predicted future demand for hydrogen would be covered by imports from other countries (35% from European countries and 55% from countries outside Europe) according to recent studies [4].

Since it is not expected that all industrialized countries will be able to generate all the green hydrogen required for decarbonizing their energy sectors within their geographical areas, large quantities of hydrogen will need to be transported over long distances and transport and storage of hydrogen will be essential in the realization of the above plans. Because transportation and storage of *gaseous* hydrogen is associated with some problems, and the use of pipelines is not always possible, so-called Power-to-X (PtX) concepts have been developed. These concepts refer to the generation of green gaseous hydrogen from green electricity and its subsequent conversion to an energy carrier X which can be further stored and transported over long distances (for example, liquid hydrogen, methanol, or ammonia). The significant thermodynamic inefficiencies and costs associated with the large-scale liquefaction and regasification of hydrogen are discussed in [5] and [6]. The inefficiencies and costs of the conversion of gaseous hydrogen to another substance (methanol, or ammonia) are however also significant. Ref. [7] provides a comprehensive review and assessment of the state of the art, challenges, and recent developments associated with all these processes.

It is apparent that, when evaluating PtX processes, the inefficiencies and costs of these processes must be added to those of water electrolysis, resulting in relatively low overall efficiencies and a high cost of the hydrogen available at the consumer site. The efficiencies of the overall process starting from electricity used to produce the hydrogen to the final product delivered at its destination are well below 50% [7], making the meaningfulness of applying these solutions at least questionable because the potential for increasing all these efficiencies is not very large. Despite all these points, a significant amount of research funds are currently allocated to PtX processes.

Finally, current plans call for the generation of large amounts of hydrogen in dry areas (e.g., northern Africa). In this case, the inefficiencies and cost of PtX processes, transportation of X, and water desalination (even if small compared to the total product cost), must be added to those of the electrolytic process for hydrogen generation, making such an overall process even less attractive. It should be noted here that the required quality of water used in electrolysis is, in general, relatively high. When analyzing plans referring to the production and use of hydrogen, the question arises, whether all these plans maximize decarbonization and, if not, under what conditions maximization of decarbonization can be achieved. These points are discussed in the next section.

3. CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH A GREEN HYDROGEN ECONOMY

We must always keep in mind that the selection of hydrogen (generated using electrical energy) as an energy carrier results more from our inability in the past years to find other more attractive solutions to decarbonize the energy supply and less from hydrogen’s attractiveness to be produced, transported, and used as an energy carrier.

First, we must recognize that from the thermodynamic viewpoint it is not meaningful to invest money and accept significant thermodynamic inefficiencies to convert electricity (which has the highest thermodynamic quality, as expressed by the exergy concept) into an inferior energy carrier (hydrogen) in an electrolytic unit. Thermodynamics shows that the theoretical capability of hydrogen to generate work (the exergy of hydrogen) is 83% of its higher heating value (the energy of hydrogen), whereas the exergy to energy ratio for electricity is 100%. This point becomes particularly clear, when the generated hydrogen is subsequently used to produce electricity. In this case, hydrogen is just used to store electricity with an expected roundtrip efficiency well below 50%. There are other concepts (e.g., batteries and, particularly, pumped storage power plants) that may offer a storage capability for electricity which is more attractive from both the thermodynamic and the economic viewpoints. In addition, from the decarbonization viewpoint, the storage of excess electricity in the form of hydrogen is only required when the electricity has been entirely generated from *intermittent* renewable resources, i.e., solar or wind. Regarding the production of green hydrogen, the main problems have always been the relatively low thermodynamic efficiency of all known processes and the high production cost.

Considering the way electricity generation units are dispatched with the renewable energy units using solar and wind energy being dispatched first, any *additional demand* for electricity for the production of supposedly green hydrogen will be covered in the next decades mainly using other energy forms: nuclear energy or, in the large majority of countries, fossil fuels. Policymakers, who are frequently in favor of establishing a hydrogen economy, base their arguments on the *average* energy mix used in a country for electricity generation, but what really matters is which energy sources are used to supply the *additional (marginal)* electricity required for an electrolytic unit to generate hydrogen. If at least one fossil-fuel power plant is in operation when an electrolytic unit is in use, then the electricity used to produce hydrogen comes exclusively from fossil-fuel energy and is definitely *not green* independently of the average amount of electricity generated from renewable sources at that time.

The hydrogen generated in this way leads to an increase in the associated costs and the overall CO₂ emissions (compared to the case without hydrogen generation) and has a negative effect on the decarbonization efforts, particularly when PtX technologies are further involved. Here we should also consider that, once electrolytic units, which are capital-intensive energy converters, have been installed, to ensure economic viability, they might be operated more or less independently of whether green excess electricity is available at a given time. Such operation would definitely not contribute to decarbonization efforts for the great majority of countries in the coming years.

Let us now consider a different aspect and assume that in a specific region A there is a given amount of excess electricity generated exclusively from renewable sources. In one option (*option I*) this excess electricity could be used for hydrogen production. The hydrogen would then be transported to and used in another region B to reduce the amount of fossil fuels used in B, e.g., in industry or in power production. A second option (*option II*) for using the excess electricity might be to directly transfer the electricity to a neighboring region C that uses fossil fuels for electricity generation at the time being considered. In *option II*, the transferred energy would be used directly in C to reduce the electricity production from fossil fuels and, thus, the CO₂ emissions in the same time period, whereas the required energy in region B would be covered by continuing to use fossil fuels. The energy demands in regions B and C are independent of the amount of excess electricity generated in region A.

Option II leads to a more efficient and cost-effective use of the excess electricity in region A and simultaneously to lower *overall* CO₂ emissions, because the potentially avoided CO₂ emissions in region B in *option I* are smaller than the potentially avoided CO₂ emissions in region C (*option II*), due to the additional inefficiencies in generating and transporting hydrogen in *option I*. If the excess green electricity generated in region A is significant and it is anticipated that fossil fuels would be used for a long time in region C, it might even be more cost effective to connect the two regions with an electric line (assuming they are not already connected) than to generate hydrogen. This comparison demonstrates that investments in green electricity generation used exclusively for hydrogen production might not be using the invested money in the most effective way to maximize decarbonization. It is apparent, however, that there are exceptions to that, for example in the cases of an island that is far away from the mainland (e.g., Island and Canary islands), where the production and storage of green hydrogen to be used later for electricity generation might be the preferred solution for decarbonization.

The above observations demonstrate the need to (a) increase the capacity of electrical interconnections among regions and countries, (b) establish new or expand existing electric grids and (c) keep the largest possible boundaries when evaluating the effects of decarbonization measures involving hydrogen. Thus, decarbonization of a city or a small geographical region through hydrogen might increase the overall CO₂ emissions, compared with the option in which the electricity used for the hydrogen production would have been used to reduce the use of fossil fuels for electricity generation in a neighboring region. Therefore, plans to decarbonize single cities, regions, or industries must be carefully evaluated considering the above facts.

The term *neo-colonization* has been used in conjunction with the efforts of some industrialized countries to speed up their decarbonization by importing hydrogen from developing countries, while the latter are still using fossil fuels to generate electricity. In these cases, part of the exported hydrogen might be generated from fossil fuels in a rather inefficient way that does not reduce the overall CO₂ emissions in the fastest and least expensive possible way. Even if the generated hydrogen is 100% green, the electricity used for its production could have been used instead to eliminate the use of fossil fuels in the exporting country before the first hydrogen for export is produced. We have not achieved much if an industrialized country manages to decarbonize its energy sector “at the expense” of one or more developing countries that are denied the maximum potential for reducing

their CO₂ emissions. All future partnerships of countries in the energy area must ensure that all the countries are at the same level (at eye level).

Since the available financial resources for decarbonization are limited, an important criterion for evaluating decarbonization options and establishing priorities is the amount of CO₂ emissions avoided per dollar invested in each option considered. In such comparisons, the system boundaries should not be local, but should include the entire Earth. Under these conditions, many decarbonization projects currently being considered should be rejected.

When establishing priorities for the use of hydrogen, hydrogen should be initially used in the sectors and processes that are the most difficult to decarbonize. Examples include the use of hydrogen in the steel, cement and glass industries, or in fuel cells used in heavy trucks as well as the use of hydrogen derivatives in the aviation sector. Plans calling for mixing green hydrogen with natural gas to use the existing pipeline network for hydrogen transportation should be abandoned because in this case hydrogen would also be used in processes and sectors that could be decarbonized more easily from the technical and economic viewpoints, like production of electricity or heat.

We must further recognize that the goal is not, and cannot be, the establishment of a hydrogen economy, as some studies suggest. *The goal is the decarbonization* of human-related operations on Earth (the largest possible boundaries). Thus, as long as the conditions for generating large *excess amounts of green electricity* in large areas are not met, a hydrogen economy would be counterproductive to the decarbonization efforts.

From the above discussion we might conclude, that as long as fossil fuels are used on a large scale to cover the demand for electricity (here we must also include the expected increases in this demand for purposes such as artificial intelligence, transportation and decarbonization of industry and the heating sector) in a country, the implementation of a hydrogen economy will lead to a significant increase in the inefficiencies, costs, and CO₂ emissions in the energy sector of the same country compared to other options that either are already or could easily become available. This becomes particularly important for decarbonization, when the additional electricity for hydrogen production is generated using coal and subsequently PtX technologies are used. Generating hydrogen from electricity produced using coal or natural gas is costlier and leads to higher CO₂ emissions compared with the option of generating the hydrogen directly from the same fossil fuels.

A hydrogen economy can only be meaningfully implemented when worldwide large quantities of excess green electricity will be available. Unfortunately, this requirement cannot be realistically achieved in the next two to three decades while ensuring economic, social and political stability, because of the following significant challenges associated with this required increase in providing green electricity [8]:

1. The capital required for new investments in renewable energies and for establishing new infrastructures (e.g., power lines) is very large. Only a relatively small portion of this capital can realistically be supplied by governments. Moreover, these investments are not yet attractive enough compared to other investment options for private investors to invest in rapidly decarbonizing the electricity generation.
2. The energy sectors of electricity generation, heat supply, transportation and industry will compete among themselves for the same decarbonization options, leaving not all options available for green electricity generation.
3. Political calculation (see for example [9]), lobbying efforts, populism (one of the main dangers and obstacles in the author's opinion), and corruption often make the implementation of required policies impossible or cause a regression in the decarbonization process.
4. The world population, which continues to rapidly increase, is not yet ready for the changes in prices, use of energy, or lifestyle that are essential for reducing the demand for energy (at least on a per capita basis) and particularly for green electricity. The public has not been educated adequately or is misinformed about what needs to be done.

A very important and still unresolved issue refers to the cost of energy in the future. We cannot expect that the decarbonization goals will be achieved in the coming 3 to 4 decades without a significant reduction in the per capita energy use in industrialized countries. The two energy crises in the 1970s and the recent price increases in Europe as a result of the Russian war against Ukraine have clearly demonstrated that an increase in energy prices leads to a reduction of the per capita energy use. These experiences have shown that a price increase above a given threshold is the most effective way for reducing this use. Here the author refers to a price increase that will not come through a war, fuel shortage, or thermodynamic inefficiencies, but through thoughtful deliberations and agreement

among main players to fight climate change. Needless to say, that no matter how well designed such a price increase will be (e.g., gradual introduction, and support of socially disadvantaged and low-income groups), it will be used for political gains by populist political parties seeking to capitalize on the economic anxieties of working people, so that even a government serious about decarbonization will likely not proceed with such required price increases. Here, an objective education of the public on decarbonization issues and solutions that contain important elements of social justice could improve the situation, but not solve the basic problem.

Since there is no realistic solution to this problem, we cannot expect that the per capita energy use will decrease and decarbonization will proceed with the speed required to avoid serious climate change effects. Here we should make two notes: (1) a well-designed energy price increase would provide the much-needed planning security in the energy-intensive industry, and (2) the goal of “affordable energy”, as formulated in the Sustainable Development Goal number 7 by the United Nations (2022), is well-intentioned, but not necessarily consistent with the decarbonization goals, because the more affordable energy is, the lower the expected efforts to save energy, and, consequently, the larger the energy use (and “waste”) per capita will be. This, combined with the continuous increase in the world population results in a continuous increase in the world demand for energy. It is obvious that each additional unit of energy required in a not fully decarbonized country (assuming it does not use nuclear energy) comes, in general, from fossil fuels and this leads to an increase in CO₂ emissions worldwide.

Finally, in the planned projects on hydrogen there seems to be an imbalance between supply and demand: on one side, many plans for supplying hydrogen exist, whereas fewer projects deal with the subsequent use of hydrogen. This imbalance is certainly also the result of all the challenges associated with the use of hydrogen. Any subsidies that might be used to change this imbalance in the very near future would mean a non-effective use of the corresponding financial resources for decarbonization purposes. No liquid market for green hydrogen exists to date and few renewable hydrogen financing deals have been closed. More than 1,400 renewable and low-carbon hydrogen projects representing \$570 billions of investment by the end of 2030 have been announced globally, although less than 7% have reached a final investment decision [10]: This last reference also provides a detailed assessment of the risks associated with green hydrogen projects and the corresponding risk mitigation strategies.

4. WHAT MUST BE DONE AND AVOIDED IN ENERGY POLICIES

Possible applications of hydrogen in various energy sectors include those in electric power generation, heat supply, transportation, and several industrial applications (e.g., production of steel, cement, synthetic fuels, and fertilizers). Prioritizing the use of hydrogen, particularly in the first decades of the establishment of a hydrogen economy, and initially focusing on the sectors that are more difficult to decarbonize are of paramount importance for the success of the hydrogen plans. With that in mind, and contrary to the current plans of many electric utilities, we should not be talking about the use of hydrogen for electricity production or heat supply in the very near future. (Christidis et al, 2023) provides a comprehensive discussion of the challenges associated with the use of hydrogen in power plants.

Calls to “double the energy efficiency”, as mentioned in documents of the European Union, mislead the public, because they are very far from being realistic for electricity generation, and are still very exaggerated, when they refer to the use of electricity. This is true not only when we consider the economic sides (costs), but also thermodynamic boundaries imposed by the second law of thermodynamics. For example, with the latest improvements achieved in combined-cycle power plants (efficiencies above 63%), we approach these boundaries, i.e., the largest part of the remaining thermodynamic inefficiencies (exergy destructions) in the production of electricity is unavoidable. Similarly, efficiencies above 48% in the conversion of coal energy in electricity will remain economically unfeasible in the coming decades.

Some priorities and some actions that need to be established possible include the following:

1. Absolute priority in the coming years and perhaps the coming decade should be given to the expansion of the use of renewable energy sources, as well as to the expansion of the electricity grids and of the interconnections among countries, which are very important for achieving the decarbonization goals faster and in a sustainable way.
2. The public must be objectively educated on the necessity of decarbonization and the real challenges associated with it and should be persuaded to accept and support higher energy prices

to reduce the “energy waste”. The way we all think about energy must be changed, if we want to succeed.

3. The use of hydrogen and PtX technologies should not be promoted now, but in later years, when the share of green electricity in a country reaches very high levels. When evaluating the role of hydrogen in the decarbonization of any sector, we should use the largest possible system boundaries and not evaluate isolated industries or cities.
4. Later, the initial goal should be to generate hydrogen for internal use or export mainly in countries where the electricity generation from renewable energy sources exceeds a given high percentage, for example, 90%, and only if it is not possible/required to export the excess green electricity to neighboring countries to reduce their use of fossil fuels.
5. The design of an *efficient* carbon pricing scheme (e.g., carbon tax) that could be implemented initially in many mainly industrialized countries has the potential to speed up the production of green electricity and to facilitate the transition to a hydrogen economy. International cooperation is of paramount importance also in this case.

Regarding the required actions for decarbonization, policymakers (as well as scientists and engineers) carry a heavy burden: They must ensure that (a) international collaboration in the energy area is maximized, (b) the profitability of private investments in the production of green electricity remains high, (c) the electric grids and the interconnections among different regions are sufficient to transfer large amounts of electricity from one region to the other, and (d) the electricity is sold to the other region at a fair price. In addition, policymakers, scientists and engineers must (1) get objectively informed and further educate the public about the necessity of all required measures (incl. higher energy prices) to combat climate change and to minimize waste, (2) prioritize these measures to maximize the benefits per invested dollar, and (3) effectively respond to misinformation and the arguments by populists. Finally, most policymakers must reconsider some of their until now advocated policies, in particular the hydrogen-related ones, while research organizations must reconsider their research priorities and the allocation of research funds.

It is understandable that each country has as one of its highest priorities to safely provide as much green energy as possible to meet its total energy demand and we cannot realistically expect an industrialized country to finance the energy transition of a developing country without the former gaining something useful out of the deal. However, deals in which a developing country agrees to provide hydrogen to an industrialized country should not be celebrated as significant contributions to decarbonization, because they are not maximizing decarbonization worldwide, and often represent some of the very expensive contributions to decarbonization, when significantly less money could be invested in other projects that would provide the same or larger long-term decarbonization effects.

Finally, at the international level there is a need for a transparent exchange of information and data. The discrepancies between nations’ pledges and reality should be reduced. Also, the environmental policies of countries must become more consistent. Approvals of large new projects involving the use of fossil fuels and the continuing use of subsidies for such fuels are certainly not consistent with long-term decarbonization efforts.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Decarbonization faces many challenges associated with political, technical, economic, and social issues. The decisions we make today will affect what is going to happen in the decades ahead. For the very near future, it is important to select the most cost effective decarbonization options; these do not yet include the establishment of a hydrogen economy.

All decarbonization options involving the generation of hydrogen should be evaluated very carefully. Hydrogen will undoubtedly play a role in the very long term energy supply. The size of this role at a given time point will depend on the ability of our society to provide large amounts of green electricity in excess of the current demand. It is not a matter of our willingness; it is a matter of the realistic capability of a democratic society to reliably provide and use green hydrogen while continuously reducing the CO₂ emissions. As long as both of the following conditions exist: (a) the hydrogen is expected to be generated mainly through electrolysis, and (b) large amounts of fossil fuels are still used for electricity (and consequently for hydrogen) generation, a hydrogen economy should not be established.

Unfortunately, when considering the energy plans of some countries, it appears that fossil fuels will continue to be heavily used to generate electricity for several more decades. For decarbonization purposes it is important to distinguish between average and additional (marginal) energies used to

produce electricity. Theoretically, and to maximize the decarbonization effect, each country should first cover practically its entire electricity demand using renewable sources and then use the generated excess electricity to produce hydrogen for internal use or for export. Therefore, absolute priority should be given to the further development of green electricity generation as well as to the expansion of the electricity grids and of the interconnections among countries before) the introduction of a hydrogen economy. It is apparent that there can be exceptions to this when, for example, the required electricity interconnections are not in place and/or the existing electrical grid is not capable of transferring large amounts of additional electricity, then local hydrogen production might become meaningful.

Given all these challenges, it seems unrealistic that a hydrogen economy would significantly contribute to decarbonization within the timeframe suggested by many recent studies. The main reason for this is that a prerequisite for decarbonization enabled by the hydrogen economy is the availability of large quantities of excess “green” electricity. In the coming decades we will be far from reaching this goal worldwide. Thus, the introduction of a hydrogen economy in some industrialized countries should perhaps, contrary to current plans, not be currently supported by taxpayers’ money. This money would be better invested in the expansion of the green electricity generation and the electric grids.

The purpose of this paper is to add to the warnings demanding significant adjustments to the energy policy referring to hydrogen of at least the countries responsible for the largest energy use. It appears that many policymakers in industrialized countries have not yet received all the pertinent information. Many current discussions and actions in political parties, the media, and scientific journals referring to hydrogen are, in the author’s opinion, giving the general public the wrong message that the decarbonization problem can be easily solved by imminently establishing a hydrogen economy, an impression that is certainly wrong. In addition, the proposed decarbonization time schedules appear unrealistic at least from today’s perspective. By misleading the public, policymakers, engineers and scientists do not ensure its full cooperation. The public must be adequately, objectively, and transparently informed about the realistic options for decarbonization and their consequences. The way we all think about energy must be changed, if we want to succeed in decarbonization.

REFERENCES

- [1] British Petroleum, 2022. bp Statistical Review of World Energy. 71st edition, London.
- [2] IEA, 2021. Global Hydrogen Review. International Energy Agency, Paris.
- [3] Incer-Valverde, J., Korayem, A., Tsatsaronis, G., Morosuk, T., 2023. Colors of Hydrogen: Definitions and Carbon Intensity. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 291, e117294, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2023.117294>
- [4] Dena, 2021. Leitstudie Aufbruch Klimaneutralität, Deutsche Energie-Agentur, Berlin, https://www.dena.de/fileadmin/dena/Publikationen/PDFs/2021/Abschlussbericht_dena-Leitstudie_Aufbruch_Klimaneutralitaet.pdf
- [5] Incer-Valverde, J., Lugo-Mayor, C., Tsatsaronis, G., Morosuk, T., 2023. Evaluation of the Large-Scale Hydrogen Supply Chain and Perspectives on the LH2 Regasification Cogeneration Systems. *Gas Science and Engineering*. 115, e205005, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgsce.2023.205005>.
- [6] Incer-Valverde, J., Lyu, Y., C., Tsatsaronis, G., Morosuk, T., 2023. Economic evaluation of a large-scale liquid hydrogen regasification system. *Gas Science and Engineering*. 119, e205150, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jgsce.2023.205150>.
- [7] Incer-Valverde, J. Patino-Arevalo, L., Tsatsaronis G., Morosuk, T., 2022. Hydrogen-driven Power-to-X: A review and multicriteria evaluation, *Energy Conversion and Management*. 266, e115814, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2022.115814>.
- [8] Papadis E, Tsatsaronis, G., 2020. Challenges in the Decarbonization of the Energy Sector. *Energy-The International Journal*. 205, e118025.
- [9] Obama, B., 2020. *A Promised Land*, Viking, p. 490.
- [10] Klingl, S., Altgeld, F., Österlein, E., 2024. Renewable Hydrogen Project Risks, Deutsche Energie-Agentur, Berlin, https://www.powerfuels.org/fileadmin/powerfuels.org/Dokumente/Renewable_Hydrogen_Project_Risks/Global_Alliance_Powerfuels_Renewable_Hydrogen_Project_Risks_final.pdf

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work has been conducted within the framework of the EXCELLEND project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement nr. 101185742.